

Vasicine *

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Späth and Nikawitz (*Ber.*, 1934, 67, 45) isolated an alkaloid $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2$ from *peganum harmala* which resembled vasicine in its melting point and other properties but the solubility of the alkaloid in acetone was not similar to that of vasicine. Vasicine crystallises from hot acetone whilst peganine was found to be more soluble. Hanford, Liang and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 2780) have determined the solubility of the alkaloid in acetone and found it to be small. The greater solubility of peganine in acetone may be due to associated impurities. Narang and Rây (*Current Science*, 1934, 2, 388) stated that vasicine is not precipitated from the solution of its hydrochloride by alkali till acidified with acetic acid. Hanford *et al* (*loc. cit.*) have found that vasicine is no more soluble in alkali than in the corresponding volume of water. The solubility of vasicine in the alkaline solution noticed by Narang and Rây was due to its retention in solution as a colloid.

There is no doubt as to the identity of vasicine and peganine, hence the name peganine is redundant (Reynolds and Robinson, *Nature*, 1934, 134, 142).

It has never been seriously suggested by us that vasicine and peganine are different. The question of identity of the two was left open by Späth. We had no peganine at our disposal but from its properties, *e.g.*, the solubility in acetone, etc., described by Späth we thought that the two may be different. The question of the acetyl derivative is a puzzling one. We have obtained a solid acetyl derivative from vasicine but its formation may be due to a profound change in the molecule, *e.g.*, the acetyl may be formed by the tautomerism of a hydrogen atom to the nitrogen atom of the amidine system as is the case in harmaline and a loss of a molecule of water from the alcoholic hydroxyl and a hydrogen atom from a neighbouring carbon atom.

* The paper was received for publication on April 29, 1935 and Prof. Späth's paper dealing with the same subject (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 699) was not available in India till 7th May.—Editor.

The structure (I) for vasicine was advanced by Ghosh, Krishna, Narang and Rây (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2740) mainly on the ground of its giving 4-oxyquinazoline by oxidation and anthranilic acid by potash fusion. The presence of an *allyl* group was suspected because of its ready reduction of a dilute permanganate solution. Späth and Nikawitz (*loc. cit.*) relied on the same test and postulated an allyl grouping in the formula (II) they advanced. It is quite unsafe to postulate an allyl grouping as it has now been proved that a secondary alcohol grouping exists in vasicine and the reduction of permanganate is due to this. Recent experiments have indicated (*cf.* Narang and Rây, *Current Science*, 1935, 3, 352) that vasicine has a cyclic structure. Full experimental details are in course of preparation.

However, the results of Narang and Rây (*Current Science, loc. cit.*), Reynolds and Robinson (*loc. cit.*), Hanford *et al* (*loc. cit.*) conclusively dispose of the formula (II) proposed by Späth *et al*.

The present experiments on the synthesis of vasicine were initiated when the structure (I) was thought to be probable. Späth and Nikawitz (*loc. cit.*) found that peganine on reduction with sodium and amyl alcohol gave a low melting base. 4-Oxyquinazoline (III) gave with allyl iodide the substance (IV) which on reduction with sodium and amyl alcohol gave an oily base not identical with the base obtained by Späth *et al* (*cf.* Narang and Rây, *Current Science, loc. cit.*, Hanford *et al, loc. cit.*).

α -Bromobutyranilide (V) did not condense with urethane to give a quinazoline and was converted into crotonanilide in poor yield by hot dimethylaniline. But action of alcoholic potash converted it into the interesting substance β -ethylindolenone (VI).

Treatment of (V) with moist silver oxide led to α -hydroxybutyranilide but this also did not condense with urethane. Itaconic anhydride condensed with aniline to give (VII).

(V)

(VI).

(VII)

It was thought that this substance after condensation with urethane and decarboxylation would furnish (I) but the initial reaction with urethane here also was unsuccessful.

o-Aminobenzamide, however, gave the substance (VIII) on interaction with itaconic anhydride which easily cyclised to (IX), but its

(VIII)

(IX)

decarboxylation did not proceed satisfactorily.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Oxyquinazoline (5.4 g.), allyl iodide (1.5 mols.) and alcoholic potassium hydroxide (10%, 1.2 mols.) in alcohol (54 c.c.) was refluxed on the steam-bath for 3 hours. The volume was concentrated to 15 c.c. and made strongly alkaline when an oily substance separated. It was extracted with ether (20 c.c.); the residue from ether solidified. It crystallised from hot petroleum ether in clusters of needles, m.p. 67°. (Found: N, 14.96. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{ON}_2$ requires N, 15.05 per cent).

0.5 G. of the above substance was distilled in steam for 30 minutes and the distillate extracted repeatedly with ether. The ethereal

solution furnished nothing indicating that the allyl group is attached to the nitrogen atom and not to the oxygen atom (*cf. J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 31, 506).

Treatment of the above substance with hydrochloric acid.—0.5 G. of the above 3-allyl-4-oxyquinazoline was dissolved in hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.16, 10 c.c.) and was heated at 110° for 2 hours when 5 c.c. more of the acid were introduced. The product was made alkaline and extracted with ether. The extract on concentration yielded 0.45 g. of the original substance (m.p. and mixed m.p.). This also proves that it is not an *O*-allyl ether.

Reduction of 3-allyl-4-oxyquinazoline with sodium and amyl alcohol.—The substance (2 g.) dissolved in amyl alcohol (100 c.c.) was reduced with sodium (8 g.) slowly under reflux. The final colour of the solution was pale yellow. It was decomposed with water (100 c.c. contact for 12 hours).

After acidification, the amyl alcohol was removed by steam distillation and the residue after extraction with ether was cooled to 0° and basified. The separated material was extracted with ether whence a liquid, b. p. 105°-108°/3 mm., was isolated. For analysis and other details *cf. Hanford et al* who have repeated this experiment since our publication in *Current Science*.

Treatment of α -bromobutyranilide with alcoholic potash.—The anilide (3.6 g.) dissolved in alcohol (50 c.c.) was treated with a solution of potassium hydroxide (1.2 mols.) in the smallest amount of water at 50°. A colourless substance (1.5 g.) separated after 20 minutes and was collected after 3 hours. After treatment with water it was crystallised from benzene in delicate colourless needles, m.p. 264°-65°. (Found: C, 74.25; H, 6.98; N, 8.75. $C_{10}H_{11}ON$ requires C, 74.5; H, 6.8; N, 8.7 per cent).

The bromoanilide (14 g.) dissolved in acetone (50 c.c.) was refluxed with silver oxide (from 17 g. of silver nitrate) for 9 hours. The filtrate on concentration furnished an oil which solidified on standing. Crystallised from water it separated in colourless needles, m.p. 89°-90°. (*cf. Annalen*, 1894, 279, 104). The condensation of α -hydroxybutyranilide with urethane did not succeed.

*Condensation of *o*-aminobenzamide with α -bromobutyryl bromide.*—*o*-Aminobenzamide (1 g.) dissolved in benzene (20 c.c.) was treated with pyridine (0.7 g.) and a solution of α -bromobutyryl bromide (1.85 g.) in benzene (10 c.c.). The mixture was treated with water after the abatement of the vigorous reaction and the product

was crystallised from hot benzene in fine needles, m.p. 144°. (Found: N, 9.56. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_2Br$ requires N, 9.82 per cent).

The above product (0.47 g.) was treated with sodium hydroxide (0.2 g. in 1 c.c. of water and 15 c.c. of alcohol) and heated to 50° for 10 minutes and then diluted with water and acidified with acetic acid. The product (2- α -bromopropyl-4-oxyquinazoline, 0.3 g.), crystallised from alcohol in fine colourless needles, m.p. 218° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.20. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2Br$ requires N, 10.48 per cent).

The above 2-bromopropyl-4-oxyquinazoline (0.5 g.) was reduced with zinc dust (5 g.) in 20 c.c. of 3% sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline filtrate on acidification with acetic acid furnished 0.2 g. of 2-propyl-4-oxyquinazoline, m.p. 200° (mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen) after crystallisation from hot dilute alcohol.

o-Nitrobenzamide.—*o*-Nitrobenzoyl chloride (6 g.) was slowly powdered with ammonium carbonate (16 g.) and warmed on the steam-bath for 2 hours. The product treated with much water furnished the *amide* (5 g.). After crystallisation from hot water, the yield is much better than recorded in literature, m.p. 176°.

o-Aminobenzamide.—To a solution of stannous chloride (6 g.) in hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.16, 6 c.c.) finely powdered *o*-nitrobenzamide (2 g.) was added in small portions with stirring, the temperature being kept at 50°-65° during the reduction for an hour. The separated double compound was collected, dissolved in water and strongly basified. After extraction with ether the solvent was distilled off, yield 1.2 g., m.p. 110°.

Condensation of o-aminobenzamide with itaconic anhydride.—The *amide* (1 g.) dissolved in dry benzene (50 c.c.) was mixed with itaconic anhydride and refluxed for an hour. The colourless substance separating was collected and crystallised from water, m.p. 174°-76° (decomp.). [Found (after drying in high *vacuo* at 100°): C, 58.0; H, 4.9; N, 11.23. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires C, 58.07; H, 4.84; N, 11.29 per cent].

The above product (1.2 g.), dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (5%, 20 c.c.), was warmed to 50° for 45 minutes. It was then cooled and acidified with acetic acid when a colourless substance separated. After crystallisation from dilute alcohol in delicate silky needles, it had m.p. 197°-98°. [Found (in material dried in high *vacuo* at 100°): C, 63.0; H, 4.48; N, 11.84. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires C, 63.29, H, 4.35; N, 12.17 per cent].